

Review of User Needs

Version 2.0

Deliverable 2.1b

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Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

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Purpose of the document

The international project Dynamic Mobility Nudge (DyMoN) is an international project under JPI Urban Europe: ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC). Following a research pathway, the project aims at advancing research and practice on the emerging topic of digital nudging and their impact in driving sustainable mobility behaviour. The project outcomes are relevant to the scientific community, smart city mobility stakeholders (managers, urban planners etc.), policy makers, as well as other practitioners engaged in the domain of sustainable mobility, such as urban living labs.

The present document D2.1b - User needs analysis - assembled under Task 2.2 - User needs collection and analysis - is a subsequent action of Work Package 2 - Repository of Nudging methods and techniques. Based on a co-creation approach for primary data collection, the analysis presented under this document provides a thorough understanding of the needs, aspirations and expectations of the user groups concerned by the nudges repository and the overall DyMoN framework. Specifically, the document presents an overview of the needs expressed by end users (citizens), as well as smart city mobility stakeholders (mobility managers, urban planners and other practitioners in the public mobility sector) from Austria, Germany and Sweden.

The document provides key insights from the analysis of the following three actions led by the DyMoN partners:

- Four international think tanks (one with female-only participants) led by Ecollective
- Eleven individual interviews (with mobility managers, city representatives, urban planners) led by Sustainability InnoCenter
- A workshop on the smart city dashboard (with five smart city managers from Austria and Germany) led by Trafficon

The document provides key learnings and implications for other work packages, helping develop the nudging repository (T2.3) and informing user-centred tasks of other work packages, e.g. proof of concept (WP4) and dissemination and exploitation (WP6).

Executive summary

The report provides insights from the analyses of user needs, collected through four transnational think tanks with end-user citizens, eleven in-depth interviews with city stakeholders and a workshop on the dashboard design involving five smart city stakeholders.

The participants voiced that their needs for transport are, as expected, guided by convenience, price and time, but also by reliability and comfort. The user needs for the future of transport in general can be summarised as general reorganisation (e.g. in communication of train delays), mobility reorganisation (e.g. car mobility restrictions), support systems for biking (e.g. car-free bike highways), improvements of convenience (e.g. home pick-up services), better/more trains & busses.

In the first two workshops citizens chose nudges about Information on the quality, safety, and availability of bike lanes; Congestion on public transport; and Push notifications about good weather and local mobility conditions as the most relevant. No ethical concerns regarding manipulation were raised, but data privacy was discussed. In the following “female participants only” version of the same workshop, discussions were visibly more open and diverse, with participants giving more space to each idea. Overall, safety seemed to be the main concern, which, whilst visible in the previous workshop, was less dominant. Here, safety is in reference to accidents and protection from other people, and one major discussion point was on the need to have more knowledge about the locations of staff, or who to report issues to when feeling unsafe.

In the fourth and final workshop transport dashboards were discussed, first in general and later in specific on the example of a dashboard for Salzburg that Trafficon had drafted. In an ideal dashboard, participants would like information about, Sunset and sunrise times (for cycling in dark or not); Points of interest in the city that are only available now (farmers market, exhibitions etc); Wind direction (to avoid cycling in headwinds); Air pollution; and Road condition. The discussion of the specific example was lively and among many ideas participants expressed an interest in the concept of a “transport score” that would show per transport option (car, bicycle, bus) how appropriate it is now to choose this option.

Eleven in-depth individual interviews have been conducted with a diverse group of smart city stakeholders, involving city representatives, urban planners and mobility managers from Sweden, Spain, Germany and Luxembourg. The analysis provides information on the needs and the experience of the participants on five key topics: ‘Sustainable transport in cities’, ‘Target achievement monitoring’, ‘Motivational methods currently used’, ‘Data collection & analysis’ and ‘Dashboard design parameters’. The interviews informed that sustainable mobility is regarded as one of the key city strategies for climate change and that infrastructural developments, actions for improved services and public transport networks are generally adopted. However, human and financial resources, knowledge and application of nudging techniques, monitoring targets achievement vary from smaller to larger municipalities. Regarding the dashboard, the majority of smart city stakeholders appreciated the possibility of adopting environmental, social and financial indicators in an impact-simulation or forecasting function. The possibility of connecting these categories of indicators would provide a comprehensive image, informing reports, impact forecasting for different events and measures (e.g. construction on the road), and justify investments in sustainable mobility. The possibility of sourcing real-time information about citizens’ commuting behaviour, network capacity, CO2

emissions and other pollutants, in a visually understandable manner (graphs) and over a period of time (to understand trends), are some of the needs expressed for the functionality of the dashboard.

In order to gather the city stakeholders' needs and requirements regarding the smart city dashboard, a workshop with five city stakeholders from Germany and Austria was held. After discussing general questions, participants were presented with the basic concept and wireframe of the dashboard. A key finding was that responsibilities for different modes of transport are spread across different departments, and that established management approaches already exist (especially mobility management). For these reasons, a management tool as envisioned in the concept did not meet the needs of the stakeholders. Instead of being a management tool for city representatives, the dashboard should therefore rather be aimed at the public and visualise the nudging approach in aggregated form as a counterpart to the citizen app.

1. Introduction: objective of user needs analysis for the DyMoN project

The DyMoN framework addresses the needs of smart city stakeholders (managers, representatives, public servants, researchers) engaged in the urban mobility agenda, on one hand, as well as of citizens, as end-users, on the other hand. Thereby, the framework is co-developed with the engagement of its primary target groups, with a particular focus on understanding their needs, expectations and the specifics of the context in which the DyMoN framework should be applied.

Specifically, the user needs analysis collects information from the following user groups:

- **End users: Citizens** as the addressed group of digital, data-based nudges and for their involvement in the creation of nudges, and
- **Smart city mobility stakeholders:** smart city managers / city representatives as initiators of digital, data-based nudges and their surrounding data sources and effects.

Data collection is done through a mixed methods approach and co-creation rationale, involving transnational think tanks with end-user citizens (citizens), as well as in-depth individual interviews and a workshop with smart city stakeholders. The data collection has an international scope, involving participants from Sweden, Austria, Germany, Luxembourg and Spain. The data collection on user needs upholds the common denominator of focusing on stakeholders from medium-sized cities (Uppsala, Sweden; Salzburg, Austria). The data collection also includes a gender perspective, providing specific information on female user needs (citizens).

2. Needs of end-users: citizens

2.1 Objective for the DyMoN project

Citizens take a central focus in the DyMoN project, as nudging for sustainable mobility takes a bottom-up rather than a top down approach. Whereas nudging research is shifting from generic nudges to 'smart nudges' (Dalecke & Karlsen 2020), even personalised nudges can be unethical for their lack of transparency and user autonomy (Luger-Bazinger et al. 2022). Therefore, DyMoN wants to switch from a paternalistic view of nudging to a co-creation of nudging and a real understanding of needs, wishes and ideas of citizens. For involved citizens, that includes:

- understanding their needs from current and future mobility systems
- understanding their expectations and aspirations for the future of mobility
- understanding potential entry points for nudging interventions
- using co-creation to really target participants and not assumptions about them
- using co-creation for designing nudges for sustainable mobility and
- achieving insights in the types of information they want to be provided with.

A variety of interdisciplinary methods that helped to gather user needs and expectations (hopes) for nudges, were used in four workshops carried out by Ecollective, Uppsala.

2.2 Method: think tanks

During Fall 2021 and Spring 2022, four online think tanks were organised to gather information about user needs. All workshops were participatory and open to the public. The participants were informed about the goals of the DyMoN project and the purposes of the think tanks, and they agreed that their contributions can be used for these purposes.

Workshop design 1: Future of mobility (general needs)

Thursday 4th November 2021, 17:00-19:00, on Zoom.

The first workshop was aimed at gathering a broad overview of the needs and expectations of the general public towards transportation. After introducing the project and the aim of the workshops to participants, they were activated for co-creation through a number of warm-up methods. One problem in gathering data on user preferences is the discrepancy between the given situation and the situation they were asked to give feedback on. To bridge this gap, users were presented with a dream journey, written and recorded by the facilitation team, that transported them into the feedback situation, namely a Monday morning in traffic. They were then asked to report on their immediate and distant expectations for transportation through an open-question online survey.

Afterwards, they were split into four different groups, in which they discussed what they wanted to keep from the current transportation system, what they wanted to change, and what they dreamt of. Again, the answers were gathered through an online survey. Finally, participants

gave feedback on the workshop through the online platform Riseup Pad. Specifically, they were asked to report on the factors that they liked most, what they would like to see improved for the next workshop, things they missed and any additional thoughts.

Workshop 1 was attended by 8 participants.

Workshop design 2 and 3: Co-creating and evaluating nudges

Workshop 2: Thursday 27th January 2022, 17:00-19:00, on Zoom.

Workshop 3: Thursday 17th February 2022, 17:00-19:00, on Zoom.

The second and third workshops were similar, with a slight adjustment in workshop three, since it was the all-female workshop. Tools included warm-up exercises to prime participants for co-creation in the first part of the workshop. After the warm-up, workshops two and three continued with an educational section about nudges, presented through a video as well as additional explanation by one of the facilitators. Afterwards, the participants were presented with four examples of nudges that were previously identified as most promising within the app-context by the research team. The categories were taken from the taxonomy of Michie et al. (2015), whereas the examples were written for the nudging categories by the research team:

1. Knowledge
 - a. What kind of specific information would help you to decide for more sustainable means of transportation?
 - b. Based on these insights you've gathered, what nudges would you personally like to receive?
 - c. And how would you like to receive these nudges? (Which context, how often?)
2. Consequences
 - a. After walking, cycling or taking public transport, how do you feel? What benefits (emotional, health) does this have for you?
 - b. In order to raise awareness of these benefits, what nudges would you personally like to receive?
 - c. And how would you like to receive these nudges? (Which context, how often?)
3. Comparing
 - a. Has someone ever inspired you to make healthier or more sustainable choices? If so, how?
 - b. What nudges would inspire you to make more sustainable transport choices, through comparison or other's approval?
 - c. And how would you like to receive these nudges? (Which context, how often?)
4. Reminders
 - a. When would you personally like to get reminders to use more sustainable transport?
 - b. What nudge reminders would you like to receive based on this?

c. And how would you like to receive these nudges? (Which context, how often?)

Participants were split into two groups and asked to brainstorm nudges for two of the categories. To ensure co-creation, the ideas were gathered on post-it-walls within the presentation. Participants were asked to both brainstorm individually and discuss their ideas with each other. This part was aimed not just to gather ideas for nudges, but mostly to ensure that participants understood the concept of nudges. Therefore, the post-its and discussions were closely monitored by the facilitators, who also attended the break-up rooms to answer emerging questions. Through this method, facilitators were able to additionally note ideas that the participants were discussing but not putting on the post-its.

A break after this first section ensured maximum mental capacity in the participants for the next section, and an opportunity to let the concept of nudging in general and their individual ideas specifically settle in. After the break, participants were activated by asking them to help the facilitators sort their previous ideas into categories, again carried out on a slide in the presentation. Following the sorting process, participants were educated about the potential ethical issues of nudging, including some pointers from the literature on how to nudge ethically. In the next part, they were asked to mark their favourite nudges with a heart symbol and the most ethical nudges in their perspective with a star symbol. Again, this was carried out on a slide in the presentation, allowing participants to also go back and forth on the slides to remind themselves of the previous tasks and their answers. The four most popular nudges were then selected for a deeper feedback and improvement round. Participants were again split into two groups, but randomised to avoid too much of an overlap between the first nudging feedback section and the second. Fruit and vegetable symbols - pineapple, mushroom, tomato and broccoli - were used to guide participants to the right groups, additionally lighting up the perceived difficulty of the task. In these groups, they were asked to write post-its in three different categories, including the following questions:

1. Ethics
 - a. What concerns would you have about this nudge, ethically?
 - b. Would you feel manipulated?
2. Preference
 - a. What do you like about this nudge?
 - b. Would this nudge motivate a friend or a family member who often drives a car?
Why or why not?
3. Improvement
 - a. What changes would you suggest to improve this nudge, and why?

Again, participants gave individual feedback and held group discussions on the categories. Finally, participants were asked to give feedback through the online platform Riseup Pad on what they liked most, what they would improve for the next workshop, what they hoped for that didn't happen in the workshops and any additional thoughts.

The sample size for workshop 2 and 3 were respectively 7 and 4 participants.

Workshop design 4: Dashboard Co-creation and Evaluation

Monday, 7th March 2022, 17:00-19:00, on Zoom

The fourth and final workshop applied a similar method with elements of warm-up, education and co-creation with the participants. However, we worked together with Trafficon to explore and develop an idea that had emerged in their work of providing a transport dashboard to citizens. After the welcome and warm-up in the digital space, the first half of the workshop asked the participants to gather thoughts and ideas for a citizen dashboard: What would a dashboard look like if you designed it? Using a Riseup Pad online collaborative word processor, participants first individually answered two questions: 1) What kind of data do you use currently to make choices about transport? and 2) What data would you like to see in such a dashboard? Afterwards, additional insights from a group conversation were added to the Pad.

The second half of the workshop started with the introduction of Trafficon and their previous work, showing their dashboard draft to the participants and then we discussed strengths, weaknesses and additions to the dashboard. Here the questions were: “What is good and should be kept in? What should be changed, and how? And if anything was possible, what would be your dream for this dashboard?”. Firstly, individual thoughts were gathered on sticky notes in the Google Slides online whiteboard. Following, participants read each other’s ideas and together created clusters of sticky notes with themes. As a next step, participants voted for their 5 favourite ideas, creating a ranking of ideas based on popularity. Finally, insights and reflections were shared in a verbal conversation and harvested in the same Google Slides environment.

Workshop 4 was attended by 5 participants.

2.3 Participants

Themes	Dates/ Duration	Characteristics of participants/ sample size	Methods & Techniques used for data collection and analysis
1) Future of transport (general needs)	Thursday 4th November, 17:00-19:00	8 participants, gender balanced, majority aged 18-35, from Sweden and Germany. Majority of backgrounds in academia.	Dream Journal, followed by qualitative analysis
2) Co-creating and evaluating nudges	Thursday 27th January, 17:00-19:00	7 participants, gender balanced, majority aged 26-35, from Sweden, Belgium, Germany and Italy. Diverse backgrounds in IT, psychology research and	Anonymous individual brainwriting to a defined nudge-themed question, followed by a small group discussion and collective harvest. Following, a prioritisation process for the most favourite and ethical ideas. The top 4 ideas were

		communication.	then further evaluated through brainwriting with “ethics, preference, improvement” categories.
3) Co-creating and evaluating nudges (women only)	Thursday 17th February, 17:00-19:00	4 participants, all women. Majority aged 26-35, from Sweden and Germany. Backgrounds in IT and project management	Anonymous individual brainwriting to a defined nudge-themed question, followed by a small group discussion and collective harvest. Following, a prioritisation process for the most favourite and ethical ideas.
4) Dashboard Co-creation and Evaluation	Monday, 7th March, 17:00-19:00	5 participants, majority women. Majority aged 26-35, from Germany and Sweden. Majority backgrounds in IT.	Anonymous individual brainwriting in a collaborative document to two dashboard-related questions, followed by a small group discussion and collective harvest. Following, a brainwriting process about the Salzburg dashboard prototype, with another collective discussion and harvest and a prioritisation process based on agreement.

Table 1. End users - citizens - Think tanks participants list.

2.4 Results and achieved insights

From the workshops, a number of insights were achieved, summarised in the tables below. Workshop 1 was used to calibrate the think tank method, and test various aspects of remote participation. The outcome of this was a more streamlined and effective workshop plan for the remaining workshops. Furthermore, workshop 1 was used to validate the insights from the literature into the main needs and expectations for the future of mobility. For workshops 2 and 3, we focused on co-creation of nudges with the specified categories of **shaping knowledge (SK), natural consequences (NC), comparison of behaviour (CB), and reminders (R)**. Workshop 3 followed the same structure as 2, but was for female participants only. The intention of having separate demographics here was to assess the differences and similarities of results between the groups, and gather unique perspectives that may not have originally shown themselves in a mixed group environment. Workshop 4 focused on the needs and expectations from citizens in a city dashboard. Below, we highlight some of the key findings from each workshop.

Workshop 1: Future of mobility (general needs)

Insights and conclusions from workshop 1

Topic 1. Individual work content feedback

Aligning with the literature analysed previously in this project, the main needs, wishes and dreams for transportation reported by participants were as follows:

Main need in transportation, reported individually:

- convenience (87,5%), price (87,5%) and time (75%) were reported as needs by most participants
- reliability was reported by 62,5% and comfort by 50% of the participants
- independence (25%), the environmental friendliness (25%), flexibility (12,5%) and health benefits (12,5%) were reported by only few participants

Immediate expectations (wishes) - meaning that could be implemented in the near future - could be sorted into five categories:

1. general reorganisation (e.g. in communication of train delays)
2. mobility reorganisation (e.g. car mobility restrictions)
3. support systems for biking (e.g. car-free bike highways)
4. improvements of convenience (e.g. home pick-up services)
5. trains & busses (e.g. higher frequencies)

Distant-future expectations (dreams) - meaning those that could be implemented in the long term or distant future - could be summarised in four categories:

1. mobility reorganisation (e.g. ban of all car mobility)
2. technology (e.g. expectations for self-driving cars)
3. public transport (e.g. all connections always on time)
4. personal futures (e.g. buy better clothing for all weather)

Topic 2. individual work methodology feedback

- The participants of this first part gave feedback that they very much liked the dream journey method.
- At the same time, this test showed the facilitators that the dream journey method, even though very fitting to achieve transportation to a situation, was limited to individual feedback. Therefore, it was decided to only use it in the follow-up workshops when individual feedback with a high level of immersion into the situation was needed.
- Through further feedback the facilitators additionally gained the insight that shared movements in the beginning and background music in the individual reflection phases were appreciated by participants.

Topic 3. Group work content feedback

In the group work phase, participant teams reported things they wanted to keep from the current transport organisation in their cities in three categories:

1. General organisation (e.g. that the Uppsala monthly bus pass is pretty cheap and that there are not many cars in Uppsala); 3 answers were sorted into this category

2. Bike (e.g. keeping good bike lanes in Uppsala or good bike parking); 11 answers were given for this category
3. Public transport (e.g. good frequency); 12 participants reported things they wanted to keep in this category

The same categories were reported for things that people wanted to change:

1. General organisation (e.g. speed limit for Voi's electric scooters), reported by 20 participants
2. Bike (e.g. installing more bike lanes in the city centre), reported by 13 participants
3. Public transport (e.g. a better connection of rural areas to the cities), reported by 11 participants

The expectations for the near future of transport were again reported alongside the same categories, even though in this category

1. General organisation included car-free cities or a free pick-up service in the morning (car-free cities being reported as wish by 75% of participants, independently)
2. For bikes they included induction powered bike lanes or commuting bike lanes.
3. Public transport was imagined to allow end to end travel.
4. Not transport-related expectations included flexible working hours to avoid major traffic, a "city of short ways" and fun transportation options.

Topic 4. Group work method reflection

- Participants reported that they liked how the times passed quickly, that they could compare different cities in the group work and that there was a nice, open atmosphere with professional facilitation. Facilitators concluded that the activation methods worked well and a team spirit was established to a satisfying degree.
- City comparisons turned out to be a very interesting but time consuming method with less comparative data than was hoped. Therefore, it was decided not to focus on city comparisons or any other comparisons in future workshops, mostly due to time restrictions.
- With these categories having a relatively high overlap to the needs and expectations for the near future reported in the individual phase, one worry was that the instructions were not entirely clear to the participants. Specifically, the differences between needs, immediate and distant-future expectations could have not been entirely clear to participants. Consequently, facilitators decided to join group discussions in further workshops to nudge them into the direction of the workshop goals - and clear up potential questions participants might have had but not asked.
- One additional reason for the reporting of answers alongside similar categories could have been that participants were not thinking holistically. To avoid any sorting bias, facilitators decided either...
 - ... to ask more narrow questions in future workshops...
 - ...or allow broader thinking by facilitating the group work accordingly (e.g. by inviting relatively silent participants to speak or adapt the applied methodology according to the needs of the situation).

- Further participant feedback indicated that participants wished to have more time for teamwork. Therefore, team or group work was planned with more time or more specific exercises in the future workshops.
- Finally, participants gave feedback that they wanted more information, especially prior to the workshop and as follow-up emails. Accordingly, “homework” was set up in the sign-up emails with reading materials for the project, nudging and mobility and follow-up emails were planned.

Workshop 2: Co-creating and Evaluating Nudges

For workshops 2 and 3, we focused on co-creation of nudges with the specified categories of **shaping knowledge (SK)**, **natural consequences (NC)**, **comparison of behaviour (CB)**, and **reminders (R)**.

When running the workshop, we noticed that most of the participants were far more active when placed in smaller groups, due to the improved interaction this generated. We received many different ideas for each category, with 12 for SK, 11 for NC and CB, and R having the largest response rate at 17 unique post-it notes.

Insights and conclusions from workshop 2

Topic 1. Dominant categories of desired nudges

In the sorting step, the dominant categories of desired nudges ranged from:

- information about infrastructure availability (e.g. bike lanes, safe parking, bike pumps),
- personal benefits of sustainable transportation (e.g. exercise and mental health),
- information about current mobility conditions (e.g. public transport availability, and traffic jams),
- the temporality of various nudges (e.g. seasonal availability, or when nudges are most effective)
- the type of media channels (e.g. via news feeds, or through popular culture such as memes)

Topic 2. Preferred nudges by participants

The nudges picked by most participants were:

- Information about the quality, safety, and availability of bike lanes
- Congestion on public transport
- Push notifications about good weather and local mobility conditions

Topic 3. Ethical concerns: data privacy

We then moved to discuss the ethical implications of these nudges in the wider context of urban mobility, their preferences, and how they might be improved.

- Surprisingly, not many participants were worried about being manipulated by nudges, even after being informed that this was a typical concern. Instead, they mostly worried about issues of data privacy; specifically their location information, how this

information was stored, and whether it would be shared with third parties. In terms of preference, a push notification about weather and traffic conditions combined with a best or safest route to work was the nudge most likely to change the opinions of friends or family members. Reasons given included the convenience of receiving such a message, and its helpfulness in new or unfamiliar locations. Suggestions to improve the nudges were related to the users ability to control data privacy aspects, and the accuracy of weather data.

- The congestion nudge had similar data privacy concerns, but participants believed it could be mitigated through anonymisation. Interestingly, and perhaps contradictory, social nudges were a popular discussion point, with the idea that participants would be more motivated to know their friends and family were planning on being on the tram or bus with them. There was also a slight concern that this nudge, by itself, might make people avoid the bus if it was congested. Hence to improve the nudge, it should be combined to include information about the congestion for other means of transportation.
- The nudges regarding quality, safety, and location of bike lanes continued the trend of data privacy concerns, but less so than previous nudges. Participants liked that it might help them avoid cycling near cars, but this seems to be more of a comment on the availability of safe bike lane infrastructure itself than the nudge. To improve this nudge, participants recommended a user-friendly visual experience that seamlessly integrated other important functionalities and different types of information that is not available elsewhere (e.g. on google maps), and takes user feedback to improve real-time accuracy.

Figure 1: Workshop 2 Idea Overview. After brainwriting nudge ideas on individual post-its, participants collaborated to sort ideas into categories they came up with. Following, each participant voted for ideas based on personal preference (green hearts) and ethics (blue circles).

Workshop 3: Co-creating and Evaluating Nudges (women only)

As mentioned, this workshop was for female participants only. Consequently, there were fewer participants than in workshop 2, but the level of engagement was increased. The discussions were visibly more open and diverse, with participants giving more space to each idea.

Insights and conclusions from workshop 3

Topic 1. Safety

- Overall, safety seemed to be the main concern, which, whilst visible in workshop 2, was less dominant.
- Here, safety is in reference to accidents and protection from other people, and one major discussion point was on the need to have more knowledge about the locations of staff, or who to report issues to when feeling unsafe.

Topic 2. Nudge suggestions and voting

- Between the nudging categories, many ideas were presented; 18 for shaping knowledge (SK), x for natural consequences (NC), x for comparison of behaviour (CB), and x for reminders (R). In the sorting stage, the most common themes were:
 - Weather related information (e.g. reminders to take jackets).
 - Safety related information (e.g. surveillance system locations, movements of local law enforcement, that the counters at train stations have personnel still working, or that controllers are in the trains and actively looking out for single travellers).
 - Congestion related information (e.g. live maps for passenger numbers on public transport). Participants expressed a preference for higher density of passengers in the evenings for safety reasons: they would prefer a busy bus over an empty train.
- Interestingly the language format on the post-its was more suggestive or provisional in the female respondents, perhaps indicating that nudges should be communicated differently to different genders.
- When voting for nudges, the responses were more evenly distributed across all ideas, with no single idea being dominant. Similarly to workshop 2, participants did not view nudges as overly manipulative, though this may have been selection bias, since the selected nudges may be perceived as less problematic. Nudges which contained reminders or helpful information were viewed as more ethically preferable.

Topic 3. Evaluating nudges

- For the nudge that demonstrated the shortest route with the best conditions, data privacy issues were raised by a few participants. In terms of preference, participants liked that all the information would be in one place, and would improve the nudge by adding other relevant data to provide a holistic view of the journey.
- There was also one participant who raised the issue that most of the nudges were for people who commute; she would appreciate suggestions that covered alternative metrics for different use cases. The example given was a parent travelling with children, where time is not that essential, but perhaps convenience, or locations of play parks en route.

- For the nudge regarding a public transport congestion map with different colours according to the number of people travelling at any given time, participants noted an ethical concern with the veracity of data, and its potential to be used by bad actors (people with negative intent). Again, this highlights a sensibility towards safety concerns. To improve it, participants also recommended a holistic and inclusive view with other functionalities.

Figure 2: Workshop 3 Idea Overview. After brainstorming nudge ideas on individual post its, participants collaborated to sort ideas into categories they came up with. Following, each participant voted for ideas based on personal preference (green hearts) and ethics (blue circles).

Figure 3: Workshop 3 Evaluations of nudge ideas. The nudge ideas with most votes were further evaluated with questions on ethics, preference and improvement. The original nudge can be found at the top of the screen in blue, the feedback from participants is on the white post-its.

Workshop 4: Dashboard Co-creation and Evaluation

Insights and conclusions from workshop 4

Topic 1. General data and dashboard preferences

- The data that participants currently use to make choices on transport, in order of popularity, are 1) weather 2) cost 3) (comparative) trip duration and 4) possible delays.
- In an ideal dashboard, participants would like the following information, in order of popularity:
 - Sunset and sunrise times (for cycling in dark or not)
 - Points of interest in the city that are only available now (farmers market, exhibitions etc)
 - Wind direction (to avoid cycling in headwinds)
 - Air pollution
 - Road condition (cobblestone, muddiness of the path, potholes)

Topic 2. Specific recommendations for the Salzburg dashboard

The most popular recommendations were:

- “Would be nice to see more graphs to see how the “more than usual” relates to other days really”
- “Option to see what recommendation for cycling is based on? When will the message change to it not being a good day? This is maybe quite personal. What weather is okay for biking?”
- “Filter for the map. One user wants to see clouds. An other wants to see road utilisation”
- There was also a discussion about making the dashboard phone friendly and/or desktop friendly. One recommendation was to provide this dashboard to local schools, public transport operators and bicycle sharing schemes, so that they can show the dashboard on big screens in public spaces.
- Finally, participants expressed an interest in the concept of a “transport score” that would show per transport option (car, bicycle, bus) how appropriate it is now to choose this option. For instance, sunny weather and no wind would increase the “cycling score”, whereas high pollution and long traffic jams would decrease the “car score”.

Figure 4: Workshop 4 Feedback on dashboard. After brainwriting feedback for the dashboard on individual post-its, participants collaborated to sort the feedback into categories they came up with. Following, each participant voted for ideas based on agreement (green hearts).

3 Needs of smart city mobility stakeholders

3.1 Objective for DyMoN project

For city representatives concerned with sustainable mobility in their cities, the DyMoN project will provide a handbook on digital, situation-aware nudging strategies as well as a data dashboard that bundles, displays and visualises relevant context and situational data on sustainable mobility. In order to create these project results, the needs, expectations and challenges of smart city mobility stakeholders were collected through individual interviews and a workshop described in the sections that follow.

3.2 Individual interviews with smart city stakeholders

3.2.1. Method

Qualitative interviews with city stakeholders have been conducted by Sustainability InnoCenter as a form of collecting primary data. As the city stakeholders constitute one of the main target audiences and intended users of the DyMoN products, in-depth, qualitative data collection and analysis was required. Smart city stakeholders is a heterogeneous group consisting of city representatives, urban strategists and planners, managers and other individuals working on the urban smart mobility agenda.

In total, 11 interviews have been conducted. Of these, one was considered to provide less insights and has therefore been used less in the analysis. The duration of the interviews varied between 45 minutes and an hour, and the interviews have been recorded for ex-post transcription. The sample size of 11 participants is represented by individuals holding positions connected to transport, mobility, sustainability and innovation in public and research institutions. The interviewees have been identified and approached by Sustainability InnoCenter, with input from other DyMoN partners.

The interview guide, included in Annex 1, has been created to address different members of the sample taking account of their specific know-how and expertise. The interview guide proposes 5 topics and additional questions for demographics. The five topics of interest are:

- Topic 1: Sustainable transport in cities
- Topic 2: Target achievement monitoring
- Topic 3: Motivational methods currently used
- Topic 4: Indicators currently used
- Topic 5: Dashboard design parameters

3.2.2. Participants

The interviewees have been selected through personal networks and via recommendations by other members of the consortium. The selection process relied on purposeful sampling, based on the criteria sought in this target group. Particularly, all respondents are engaged in planning or strategy building for urban mobility, public governance, sustainability and innovation, at a

technical implementation or political level. The interviewees belong to different municipalities, with different sizes, to provide a broader perspective on the varying needs of those.

The interviewees have been approached via email and introduced to DyMoN, the scope of the research and use of their answers. The interviewees agreed to having their answers included in the research of city representative user needs.

Name	Role	City/Region, Country
Participant 1	Strategist	Uppsala, Sweden
Participant 2	Manager (product owner) with a focus on traveller information	Uppsala, Sweden
Participant 3	Innovation lead	Uppsala, Sweden
Participant 4	Urban planning specialised in mobility	Visby, Sweden
Participant 5	Project manager within sustainable mobility	Tomelilla, Sjobo, Sweden
Participant 6	Strategist in mobility	Stockholm, Sweden
Participant 7	Mobility planner	Uppsala, Sweden
Participant 8	Ecosystem leader, Professor	Santander, Spain
Participant 9	Transport planning and mobility planning and research	Munich, Germany
Participant 10	Project manager within sustainable mobility	Uppsala, Sweden
Participant 11	Engineer, member of the municipal council	Leudelingen, Luxembourg

Table 2. Smart city mobility stakeholders individual interviews participants list

3.2.3. Achieved insights from the interviews

Topic 1. Sustainable transport in cities

Questions under this topic inquired about the cities' response to climate change and existing environmental and mobility goals.

- Mobility is seen as instrumental in achieving the city's, the national and EU climate neutrality goals, for reducing air particles, pollution and the heat island effect of the city.
- Responses to climate change vary with each city; cities work with both soft and hard measures to reduce carbon emissions, examples of measures currently applied
 - promoting biking and public transport;
 - switching to a fully electric bus fleet;
 - increasing the capacity of trains and public transport systems;
 - providing more affordable or free transportation for determined periods of time.
- To support their sustainable mobility agenda, some cities are developing pilot programmes for bikes/scooter mobility; examples include
 - developing apps for bike/scooter mobility;
 - improving rental services.
- Some cities experience challenges providing facts and supporting arguments for the mobility development agenda and environmental goals -> they require more data connecting environmental goals and mobility goals.

Topic 2. Target achievement monitoring

Questions under this topic inquired about ways in which cities monitor their sustainable mobility targets.

- The respondents gave limited insights on the topic, as their role includes target monitoring to a lesser extent.
- Some targets currently monitored include
 - Citizens' mobility behaviour & events participation
 - Citizens' travelling behaviour to and from work
- Measuring progress towards sustainable mobility targets is a challenge for the following reasons:
 - Smaller municipalities have less resources and/or competencies, e.g. tools for measuring air pollution and emissions
 - There is no evaluation and follow up on the monitoring done (e.g. through surveys) -> leading to insufficient insights on the progress on targets

Topic 3. Motivational Methods

Questions under this topic inquired about the existence and use of motivational methods to influence citizens' sustainable mobility behaviour. The topic also inquires about the results gained, the drivers and barriers to these techniques.

- The concept of nudging as means to drive behavioural change was mentioned only by one respondent; the other interviewees mentioned the use of different motivational techniques to drive sustainable mobility behaviour
- In most cases, the interviewer had to explain to the interviewees what a nudging technique is and how it can be implemented -> this can be attributed to a lack of knowledge or use of the concept and its uses by the respondents
- Participants mentioned several **motivational techniques and channels currently used** to support or drive sustainable mobility behaviour. These are:
 - Information sharing, mentioned by 8 participants: examples include providing updates about schedules and possible disruptions.
 - Communication, mentioned by 6 participants, also referred to as 'direct communication techniques': examples include providing direct information through meetings and seminars - these events can have an educational purpose as well (e.g. benefits of sustainable mobility, road signs and safety for cyclists).
 - Digital platforms and apps, mentioned by 6 participants, are used as means to support other techniques (e.g. information sharing): examples include displaying real time information on big screens in mobility hubs (referred to as 'infotainment') or bicycle maps, that provide real time information about state and safety of bike lanes .
 - Pricing techniques and incentives, mentioned by 3 participants, can be considered a behavioural economic nudge: examples include offering free tickets in certain periods of the year (especially summer), road and parking fees to discourage car use.
 - Technological advances, mentioned by 6 participants: examples include the development of car & bike sharing systems or promoting electrical cargo bikes and electrical vehicles; however, the success of the latter is connected to the available network of recharging power stations, participants raised the need to improve this infrastructure.
 - Events and educational activities, mentioned by 3 participant; examples include events such as 'The Biking night' or visits at local school to discuss mobility in the context of European mobility week
 - Nudges, mentioned by 1 responded: examples ease access to information on where to rent or repair bikes.
- Applying the above mentioned motivational techniques has been associated with the following insights on the **achieved results**:

- Participants inform about the positive effect of using motivational techniques and sustainable mobility behaviour.
- The insights gained from using these motivational methods are discussed under two categories, with their specifics:
 - Quantitative insights: easier to measure, these are used in the planning and decision making processes.
 - Qualitative insights: respondents mentioned challenges in measuring and gaining qualitative insights.
- The achieved results and insights provided information on the types of systems and mobility projects needed to be further developed and the changes to be considered
- The participants referred to the following **drivers and barriers to using motivational techniques**:
 - Environmental drivers: reducing CO2 emission, air and noise pollution;
 - Social barriers: overcoming citizen resistance, also referred to as 'mental barrier' (e.g. shifting behaviour of regular car users), elderly or impaired citizens;
 - Economic barriers: bureaucracy and political resistance, associated with limited financial resources, leading to a lack of feasibility studies, or investments in infrastructure development.

Topic 4. Indicators used

Questions under this topic inquired about the type of indicators currently used by the smart city mobility stakeholders, as well as the indicators that would be useful but are currently out of reach.

- Seven out of ten respondents stated that to some extent they apply indicators in their work on mobility - these mostly focus on environmental factors.
- The list below provides insights into the type of environmental, social and economic indicators used by the participants:
 - Environmental indicators are used to measure the level of different pollutants and emission types (co2, pm10 and noise), examples include:
 - Air pollution
 - Pollutant emissions per capita, broken down by the mode of transportation used by the inhabitants
 - Resource efficiency such renewable energy used in different transport modes
 - Allocated infrastructure (parking lots and roads) per capita

- Spared emissions calculation (i.e. comparing how often people use sustainable mobility instead of cars)
- Social indicators, examples include:
 - Citizens' satisfaction rate when using different modes of transport (collected through surveys)
 - Citizens' health and the impact of exposure to air and noise pollution
 - Number of citizens walking or travelling by bike monitored for overtime developments and their impact on citizens' health and wellbeing
- Financial indicators, examples include:
 - Transport cost per capita
 - Congestion cost per capita
 - Reliability rate on transport modes

Respondents showed interest in the topic of promoting collaboration between cities and municipalities and learning from each other's cases.

Unavailable Indicators

As mentioned before, different cities have different resources on the topic, with smaller municipalities experiencing increased scarcity. Some of the unavailable but needed indicators, data and tools mentioned are:

- Air pollution and emissions (co2, pm10, noise) and the necessary tools,
- Automated passenger counting systems installed on trains, buses and trams,
- Applications using real-time information about use of public transport modes,
- Applications to measure passengers' satisfaction rate,
- Feasibility studies estimating spared emissions by change of mobility behaviour,
- Means and tools for improved collaboration among citizens living in the same neighbourhood (car and bike sharing),
- Age and gender disaggregated data on citizens' mobility behaviour,
- A holistic view of all required data to inform the decision-making processes.

Topic 5. Dashboard parameters

Questions under this topic inquired about the smart city mobility stakeholders' needs and expectations for the dashboard. The questions focused on various sub-topics, as addressed below:

A. Functional features

Based on their needs, the interviewees expressed their interest for the following functional features to be included in the dashboard:

- Impact estimation / forecasting function: examples include displaying the impact of changes in road network and new mobility infrastructure, impact on emissions by applying certain measures, estimation of cost/benefits from developing or making changes in the transport network, including the economic consequences of inaction on sustainable mobility projects -> this would also provide meaningful insights in justifying investments and support for the sustainable mobility agenda.
- Information about citizens' commuting behaviour and the traffic density, based on the current capacity of public transport -> this would provide insights into parts of the network that are over- / under-utilised.
- Information on what motivates citizens (e.g. in the post-pandemic context, how to motivate citizens to return to public transport).
- Counting function for carbon emissions & sound disturbances.

The trustworthiness and functionality of the dashboard is linked to its capacity to provide context specific information & a holistic overview - working with one feature should represent a tradeoff or limit having a comprehensive view of the municipality.

Figure 5. Dashboard functionality - frequency of answers

B. Elements

Separate elements (charts, maps, tables) or a combination thereof is preferred by all respondents, depending on the purpose and the audience of the reports, for example: when disseminating to citizens and politicians, simple and clear elements (charts) are considered best. Specifically, the following elements are preferred:

- Charts are preferred to assess developments & trends over time, considered as the easiest elements to understand;
- Maps are preferred for visualising traffic volumes, the flux and direction, and emissions; interactive maps and maps that update daily and weekly would be preferred to monitor the context and assess developments over time;
- Tables: views are divided; most of the times, tables are not preferred, as they require specialised (statistical) expertise to be read. Their use depends on the degree of specialisation and expertise of the user or the target group for the report.

Figure 6. Dashboard elements - frequency of answers

C. Social, environmental, economic factors

The participants reflected on each of the three factors inquired in the context of their functionality on the dashboard:

Economic factors, mentioned in 5 out of 9 answers

- Referred to by the participants as very useful for reporting on public funds spending;
- Hence, economic factors are most useful for and preferred by political actors, in the decision making process;
- For the dashboard, the participants mentioned that data on economic factors would help generate budget estimations, and financial costs for investments on sustainable mobility projects;
- Having economic factors interlinked with social and environmental impacts can be useful in justifying claims for budgets and investments in sustainable mobility. A great benefit would come from having environmental and social

factors (e.g. climate and health) translated into costs (e.g. financial consequences for action or inaction).

Environmental factors, mentioned in 5 out of 9 answers

- Referred to as the most used and useful in the context of cities' climate action;
- In the context of the dashboard, the respondents expressed their wish for environmental factors to be applied as overlays to maps, visualising corridors of pollution, for both sound and carbon emissions.

Social factors, mentioned in 4 out of 9 answers

- Examples of social factors indicated by the participants are safety or attractiveness of a certain area based on its connectivity (e.g. safety in public transport, at late hours).
- In the context of the dashboard, the respondents expressed their wish for social factors to be applied as overlays to maps, to help visualise specific social factors for selected geographies.

Figure 7. Summary of economic, environmental and social factors and their functionality on the dashboard

D. Time scales

- Needs vary depending on the department using the dashboard/report, for example: long term developments & predictions are useful for those engaged in strategic development and planning, short term updates are useful for those in a technical implementation/operational capacity.
- Other mentions made by the participants to having time scales on the dashboard include:
 - To have an over time comparison function is considered useful to inform yearly developments,

- To have a comparative view based on different geographical areas from the same municipality and between different municipalities (with disaggregated data for rural vs urban settlements).
- Monitoring over time can help provide baseline information for future developments - lack of baseline data is considered a current challenge in sustainable mobility planning.
- Specifics time scales preferred include: monthly, quarterly and yearly, daily and weekly.

E. Evaluation of existing infrastructure and budget estimation & the potential of the dashboard to overcome challenges

- Partly due to a shortage of resources, some cities conduct no measurements or estimations on the impact of certain measures on sustainable mobility, and no evaluation on the current infrastructure and the impact on future investments -> the dashboard can be an asset by providing large amounts of systematic information, broken down per indicators of interest, if the service is not costly and it can be used by stakeholders possessing different levels of expertise.
- It is seen as beneficial to bring more information on social, environmental and economic factors into the decision-making process -> the dashboard can help provide insights on all indicators separately and - if possible - interlinked, helping justify investments that otherwise are seen as too expensive (e.g. based on citizen satisfaction, environmental impacts).
- Structural issues (e.g. access to infrastructure, capacity of the network, length of the trip), political environment or embedded mobility behaviour are still considered as main drivers for the citizens' choice for mode of mobility -> for these reasons, some participants question the use and impact of such a dashboard.

3.3. Group discussion: workshop smart city dashboard

As preparation for the user needs workshop, Trafficon developed a first concept and a wireframe of the smart city dashboard. Accordingly, the target group of the dashboard are smart city managers, city representatives and other stakeholders in the context of urban mobility. The concept includes the following core functionalities:

1. Visualising the current traffic / mobility status based on aggregated data (e.g. current traffic congestions, weather, air pollution, noise...)
2. Detection of problematic states and issuing of warnings (e.g. air pollution, traffic congestion)
3. Recommendation and /or activation of suitable nudges
4. Evaluation of effectiveness of nudges

Figure 8. Wireframe / visual draft of the dashboard concept as used in the workshop

3.3.1. Method

The goal of the workshop organised by Trafficon was to analyse the stakeholders' needs and requirements regarding data, software and interface. For this reason a workshop format was chosen. In this way the participants can discuss different perspectives and add their opinion to suggestions from other participants.

The participants were informed about the goals of the DyMoN project and the purposes of the group discussion, and they agreed that their contributions can be used for these purposes. After that the main part started with some general questions based on the interview guideline which was developed for the interviews with smart city managers by Sustainability InnoCenter. The questions covered different topics regarding the goals and actions to promote environmentally-friendly transport options, as well as about data they use to monitor mobility. The workshop participants were asked the following questions:

- Have there been any plans in your jurisdiction to promote sustainable mobility? If so, which ones? What has already been implemented?
- What are the current environmental and mobility goals?
- What metrics do you use to monitor sustainable mobility goals and progress?
- Have attempts been made to influence mode choice, and if so, how?

- What mobility/environmental data do you see as relevant? What data are you currently using?
- In an ideal world, what data would you like to have available?

In the last of the group discussion part a wireframe of the dashboard and its core features were presented to the participants. In this way the concept of the dashboard was discussed and the requirements of the mobility managers were documented for the further development of the dashboard concept.

Figure 9. Workshop notes

3.3.2. Participants

In order to encourage discussion from different perspectives and backgrounds, five experts from different regions and cities in Germany and Austria were invited to a joint workshop. The details of the participants are listed in the table below.

Table 3. Smart city managers dashboard workshop participants list

City / region (size of the city or region)	participant	Role/ background
City of Frankfurt am Main (~750.000 inhabitants)	Participant 1	mobility management (planning, conception, modelling)
Region of Frankfurt am Main (~2.4 Mio. inhabitants)	Participant 2	Mobility management and traffic management with focus on regional cooperation in the projects
City of Munich (~1.5 Mio inhabitants)	Participant 3	mobility control and development of mobility strategies
City of Salzburg (~150.000 inhabitants)	Participant 4	city planning and smart city
Region of Stuttgart (~2.8 Mio. inhabitants)	Participant 5	mobility management and traffic management

3.3.3. Achieved insights from the workshop

Insights regarding the smart city dashboard design

- Mobility (traffic) forecasts were considered a highly relevant feature for a smart city dashboard. For example, for upcoming events where more traffic congestion are predicted or simulations of the mobility distribution in case an accident happens and certain roads are closed / partly closed.; another scenario is to predict density of traffic in directions of touristic locations for example in the case of snow.
- Information about public transport capacity was seen as relevant; e.g. information about free capacity to take bikes in the train was requested. Additionally, information about the departing intervals of the train/bus and the connecting trains/buses.
- The participants gave some suggestions for possible nudges: Information/recommendation to use P+R spots in case of different mobility scenarios; recommendations for leisure mobility to visit less crowded spots or recommendations for train or bike use.
- The monitoring of already existing mobility management actions, for example, different programs for the traffic/road lights and coordinated lights were mentioned.

However, responsibilities for different modes are spread over different departments. A fully intermodal mobility management was discussed, but is currently still a vision for the future.

- Relevant data which should be available and monitored in the dashboard was, above all, all kinds of emission data like CO₂ and NO_x. Additional data about noise, travel time of public transport, travel time of private transport and traffic intensity was also seen as relevant.
- Data that is currently not available but would be important for better mobility management in the future are: weather data, occupancy rate in trains, occupancy of P+R spots and bike parking spots, extensive air quality measurement over the whole city/ region.
- For the dashboard a threshold monitoring of air quality was requested because that is an important factor for the city managers to take action.
- An aspect which was stressed by the participants was the possibility to forecast mobility scenarios with the dashboard. This was important for them to take action as early as possible which can help to keep traffic congestions manageable and lower the emissions.
- Due to distributed responsibilities (e.g. between motorised individual transport and public transport), there is currently no clear target group in the city administrations for the planned dashboard.

Conclusions for the project

- Instead of taking up well-established approaches from mobility management, the dashboard should focus entirely on the topic of nudging.
- Instead of being a management tool for city representatives, the dashboard should therefore rather be aimed at the public and visualise the nudging approach in aggregated form as a counterpart to the citizen app. Citizens and city representatives should get an overview of the current mobility situation in the city (e.g. air pollution, mobility situation), as well as nudging conditions (e.g. good weather: nudge for cycling and walking; low public transport utilisation: nudge for taking a bike on public transport). This creates awareness and transparency regarding the nudging methods used.

4 Summary of implications & key learnings for the DyMoN framework

Implications & key learnings from needs of end users - citizens

WP# / D#	DyMoN result	Implications & key learnings
WP2 D2.2	Nudging repository and handbook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The workshops showed that the repository is a good framework for the nudges. It also showed that the nudges needed to be developed further through co-creation to gain a high level of participant acceptance. This results in the learning that the repository is only a baseline that needs to be developed further and thereby opens more opportunities for explicit application. We were able to show that there are only minor ethical concerns and participants were generally not worried about manipulation. They were instead concerned about the safety of their data. Solutions to those concerns were co-created in the workshops, for example through transparency and data sharing control.
WP3	Nudging dataHub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop participants did not report ethical concerns about the nudges. This does not imply that manipulative nudges should be used within the proof of concept phase but instead that we as researchers need to be cognisant of our responsibilities towards our users and their data rights. Within the co-creation process, participants stated their preferences for what kind of information they would like to receive. This is a baseline for both the co-created nudges and further nudging co-creation (and therefore also WP4). Workshop participants were generally concerned about data privacy, hence the Data Hub should have transparent user data policies. Presumably it is GDPR compliant, thus data privacy issues should not arise.
WP3	Nudging city dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We were able to co-create general dashboard needs and expectations with citizens, and review and expand on a draft by Trafficon for a dashboard together with citizens. The draft was a good starting point for discussion but one central learning of the workshop is that it cannot be used as is but instead needs to be reworked with the insights from the workshop. Most feedback from participants related to a wish for more contextual information: weather distribution, aggregate 'transport score' and

		underlying reasoning.
WP4	DyMoN proof of concept demonstrations - Salzburg Field study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The co-creation results give a baseline for the proof of concept in Salzburg by providing specific nudges that can be implemented in the app to be tested for effectiveness.
WP4	DyMoN proof of concept demonstrations - Uppsala Hackathon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Furthermore, they give a baseline for the Hackathon and proof of concept in Uppsala by providing specific application examples to show to business participants and software engineers.
WP5	Project evaluation and impact assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A new network of participants around Europe, ready to engage in proof of concept testing or other workshop tasks.
WP6	Dissemination & Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens are of course a highly heterogenous group and dissemination & exploitation should not exclude members by means of outreach and use of technical language.

Implications & key learnings from smart city mobility stakeholders

WP# / D#	DyMoN result	Implications & key learnings
WP2 D2.2	Nudging repository and handbook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The knowledge and contextualised use of 'nudges' is limited among smart city mobility stakeholders => the concept of nudging & its use should be well described in the handbook (key learning from individual interviews).
WP3	Nudging Data Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The trustworthiness of nudges is perceived as dependent on their truthfulness and relevance to the local context and their degree of customisation (e.g. based on the needs of the municipality, where the size, geography etc. plays a differential role) => The Data Hub should provide a wide range of situation-aware nudges, relevant to the local context (key learning from individual interviews).
WP3	Nudging city dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart city mobility stakeholders are interested to learn from the experience and challenges of similar municipalities => the dashboard could grow to include resources, cases and possibly a platform for connecting cities (key learning from individual interviews). There is a strong interest in having an impact estimation for different applied mobility measures, connecting the sustainable mobility agenda with social, environmental and economic factors => the dashboard should include a function that tailors

		<p>reports on impact estimations, connecting various indicators and issuing reports for different target groups and purposes (e.g. political forums). This would support the case of allocating local/regional/national funds for sustainable mobility, financial costs for investments and financial costs for inaction on the given project (key learning from individual interviews).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Smart city mobility stakeholders need real-time estimations on density and direction of commuters, network capacity and possible overloading, construction work etc. => Such real time data and the effect of using nudges must be available in order to inform their decision for the current context (key learning from individual interviews). ● There are competing interests and/or tradeoffs in using certain factors (e.g. a suggested route by bike can have environmental benefits but social drawbacks - by length, safety of the trip, etc.) => the dashboard should beware of bias and one-sided benefits; instead it should provide an objective overview of pros and cons that the dashboard user on both sides of the spectrum should be aware of (key learning from individual interviews). ● Smart mobility city stakeholders is a heterogenous group: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) by professional roles, with varying degrees of strategic/operational roles and city needs => the dashboard should offer a variety of elements, reports and a highly customizable experience depending on the user, the particularities of the city and the target group of the report; (b) by competences, resources, depending on the size of the municipality => the dashboard should be an affordable and highly accessible tool to fit varying human and financial resources (key learning from individual interviews). ● The dashboard should not be a management tool for city stakeholders only, but give an aggregated view on nudging approaches for the public (key learnings from (mobility) traffic managers workshop).
WP4	DyMoN proof of concept demonstrations - Salzburg Field study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Based on the challenges expressed by the smart city mobility stakeholders, the proof of concept can adopt and test the following challenge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Structural challenges connected to the available infrastructure and resources, length of commute or access to the public network in remote areas, can still be the primary factors that affect citizens' mobility behaviour; <u>what combination of situation-aware digital nudges is the most effective in persuading, driving</u>

		and maintaining behavioural change under uncontrollable external challenges? (key learning from individual interviews).
WP4	DyMoN proof of concept demonstrations - Uppsala Hackathon	
WP5	Project evaluation and impact assessment	
WP6	Dissemination & Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Smart city mobility stakeholders is a diverse and highly heterogeneous group, with varying knowledge of nudging as a concept or technique => dissemination & exploitation should avoid exclusion of its members by means of outreach and use of technical language.

References

Dalecke, Sandor and Karlsen, Randi. 2020. "Designing dynamic and personalized nudges." In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Web Intelligence, Mining and Semantics*, pp. 139-148.

Luger-Bazinger, Claudia, Marquez, Rodessa M., Harms, Carlotta, Loidl, Martin, Kaziyeva, Dana and Hornung-Prähauser, Veronika. 2022. "Ethics of digital, data-based nudges: The need for responsible innovation". Presented at The XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference "Innovating in a Digital World", held in Copenhagen, Denmark on 05 June to 08 June 2022. Event Proceedings: LUT Scientific and Expertise Publications.

Annex: interview guide

Introduction

As you are aware, cities now have a great opportunity to reduce carbon emissions through reforming transportation by making proper mobility choices.

Employing soft measures known as 'motivational techniques' has been found as a feasible option for local governments to modify people's habits.

Meanwhile, as one outcome of the DyMoN project, the creation of a 'Smart city dashboard' that would assist city planners in implementing long-term strategic goals while monitoring the present state of the system has been proposed.

Through this interview, we want to learn about your needs, so that we can create a tool that properly meets the users' demands.

Demographics

1. Could you please introduce yourself, considering your current role and responsibilities?
 - 1.1. How long have you been working for the city?
 - 1.2. What is your main responsibility? (Probe)

Topic one: Sustainable transport in cities

2. How has the city responded to climate change and has changed its mobility strategies?
 - 2.1. Do you have any examples of how things have changed?
3. Are you aware of any regional planning considering environmental or transportation goals?
 - 3.1. Could you please elaborate more in terms of desired (or planned) goals to be achieved?

Topic two: Target achievement monitoring

In case the interviewee is a policy maker:

4. How does the city monitor its status in sustainable mobility?
 - 4.1. Would you please elaborate more in terms of methods and strategies?

Topic three: Motivational methods

5. Have you tried to influence people's habits and behaviours so that one may choose more sustainable modes of transportation? For example, promotion activities, marketing and communication, cultural interventions and so on.

- 5.1. Could you elaborate more on the results gained?
- 5.2. What were the main drivers and barriers while implementing these behavioral interventions?

Topic four: Indicators used

6. Which environmental and mobility indicators (such as air pollution, traffic jams, and so on) are used and are helpful for you?
7. What other indicators in terms of mobility, environmental or even public health may be useful, but are currently out of your reach?

Topic five: Dashboard design parameters

Considering a smart city dashboard, that aims to help you in your decision-making by presenting useful environmental and mobility indications, and finally by delivering motivational methods that are completely customised to the situation:

8. Which functional features are you looking for?
9. Which elements should a Dashboard include, e.g., charts, maps, tables?
10. Which of the social, environmental, or economic factors (scale or axes) do you prefer for the reports?
11. Which time scales should a dashboard cover (current/short-term, years/long-term)?
(This question would be asked if time allows us)
 - 11.1. Which time scale is most important, weekly, monthly, yearly? (This question would be asked if time allows us)

In case interviewee is a policy maker, or a city manager: (This question would be asked if time allows us)

12. Do you think that evaluation of existing infrastructures and budget estimation could be a challenge in your decision-making process?
 - 12.1. How can this tool assist you in overcoming this challenge?